

Optimizing the Approach to the Extreme Retrieval Mission for BYU Mars Rover

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Abstract—The Extreme Retrieval Mission of the University Rover Challenge requires operators to remotely drive a Mars Rover vehicle over varying terrains and manipulate various objects. The wheels of the BYU Mars Rover vehicle often slip on loose terrain, thereby losing traction, especially on slopes and hills. Additionally, the true geometry of the arm is unknown due to manufacturing and assembly uncertainty. We propose to use optimization techniques to overcome these difficulties. A genetic algorithm succeeds in identifying the proper voltage for each of the six wheels to maintain constant velocity over changing terrains, and a constrained gradient-based optimizer identifies the true link lengths of the arm. These results allow for added versatility during the University Rover Challenge.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Extreme Retrieval mission of the University Rover Challenge, which is held annually in Utah, USA, requires teams to remotely navigate a rover vehicle to a given gps coordinate and perform various manipulation tasks. The operators must remain in a base station with no visual contact with the rover. All information must be conveyed to the operators through sensors on the rover vehicle. This paper addresses two of the challenges that arise in this mission: maintaining traction on unfamiliar terrain and calibration of the arm for manipulation using camera feedback.

The BYU Mars Rover that was fielded in the 2019 and prepared for the (cancelled) 2020 competition has a 6-wheel rocker-bogey chassis that maximizes contact with the ground and a 6-degree-of-freedom robotic manipulator, both of which can be seen in Figure 1. The rover is teleoperated from a base station using xbox controllers, one for driving and one for controlling the arm.

When driving the rover, a lack of traction on loose terrain can lead to difficulty maintaining a constant heading and navigating slopes and hills. In this paper, we present an approach to determine optimal voltage commands to maintain traction and keep a constant speed for the rover as a whole with consideration given to operator input.

It is also difficult to perform complex or fine manipulation tasks with only camera feeds. Additionally, manufacturing difficulties presented by the equipment available for composite machining at BYU make tight adherence to design tolerances unlikely, thereby changing the forward kinematics of the manipulator. In this paper, we present a kinematic calibration of the BYU Mars Rover arm. This calibration will account for manufacturing errors and allow operators to more effectively implement inverse kinematics to manipulate various

Fig. 1. The BYU Mars Rover

objects. Additionally, it could allow for the automation of some manipulation tasks through visual servoing.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Wheel Control

Many methods have been proposed for wheel control systems for different types of ground vehicles. Although the literature covers a wide variety of such methods, this review will focus on two methods related to how electric vehicle can operate efficiently with energy and how to operate in changing terrain. The first method is proposed by Iida and Tedrake [1]. In their research, they formulated an optimization technique based on a reinforcement learning algorithm. Iida and Tedrake's approach is able to tackle wheel control in a terrain with continuously changing surface conditions. This method could be beneficial to the application of mars rover. The other method is proposed by Lin and Cheng [2]. In their research, they distributed power to different wheels based on different modes of driving condition. By doing so, energy can be provided to the wheels that require the most power at any given moment. This method can reduce energy consumption rate which is desirable for vehicle relying on battery to provide power.

B. Arm Calibration

In order for the rover to place the robotic arm at a desired location, it is important for the central controlling system to

recognize the relative displacement and pose of the robotic arm. Taylor and Kleeman [3] proposed to implement hand-eye calibration method with Kalman filter to estimate the pose of the end effector of the robot. By doing so, robot calibration system can handle large position errors without sacrificing important information of calibration process. Renders et al. [4] proposed a different approach implementing a maximum likelihood technique to search for geometrical errors between the desired position and the end effector position. This approach, according to their results, can reduce the mean error of the distance between end effector and desired location by a factor of 15. These two approaches can improve the positioning and localization of robotic arm quite effectively. However, these two methods are not specifically designed for robot with a moving platform. Du et al. [5] addressed arm calibration for robot with a mobile platform. Their research utilized a relative manipulability index and global manipulability map to assist the robotic system during the localization process. This method can increase the accuracy by reducing errors between the desired location of the robotic arm in a continuous changing environment caused by moving of the whole robotic platform. Lastly, one method that can reduce cost of the localization is from Dantam et al. [6]. In their research, they implement visual tracking techniques to track on features of the robot. By doing so, the robotic system can know the location of the arm without using hardware like encoders. In this case, a single camera is sufficient to locate the robotic arm.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Wheel Control

1) *Model*: The biggest problem with wheel control with the Mars Rover is that wheels will regularly slip or spin as they lose traction on the varied terrain encountered while driving. The goal of this project was to minimize the difference in wheel spin rates by controlling the voltage to each wheel individually.

The developed function models the dynamics of each of the six wheels as a DC motor, with the varied terrain simulated by a vector that has an external torque load for each wheel simulating the friction the wheels should feel. Each motor is modeled using a given input voltage as design variables and external load torque as parameters, and solved for spin rate using an ordinary differential equation solver. The ordinary differential equations were derived from the commonly used model of a DC motor:

Fig. 2. Simple DC motor Model

$$\dot{i}_1 = (V_s - R * i - K_v * \omega) / L \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\omega}_2 = (K_v * i - \tau - c * \omega) / I \quad (2)$$

In this model, V_s is the design variable, while τ is a parameter that varies and represents the differing resistances the individual wheels will feel while driving. The rest of the parameters (R, K_v, L, I, c) are known from manufacturer-supplied data sheets.

In summary:

It was planned to minimize range of wheel spin rates with respect to voltage supplied to each wheel, subject to maximum and minimum voltages to each wheel for a total of 12 constraints

Due to the nonholonomic characteristic of the vehicle kinematic model, it is not simple to solve the problem with equations of motion and the vehicle dynamics model. It was decided to tackle the problem from the level of motor dynamics. Further investigation will need to be performed in the future.

After building an initial dynamic model of all six wheels, the function was modified to take a user input of a desired spin rate, which directly correlates to rover speed. Then, instead of minimizing the range of wheel spin rates, the function was set to minimize the maximum difference between the actual rotation rate of the wheel and the desired, or input rotation rate. This modification was simple, but we felt it allowed for a more usable function with the goal of implementing it in the actual Mars Rover robot.

2) *Optimization*: This six-dimensional model was very difficult to visualize or even develop a general idea of the shape the function could take, so deciding on an optimization scheme was more difficult than anticipated.

The natural starting point was to optimize the function with a simple constrained optimizer `fmincon`, as provided in the default MATLAB optimization toolbox. Due to the differential model nature of the function to be minimized, finding analytic solutions for gradients was impossible, so we stuck with the constrained optimizer's default numerical gradient method. This optimization method yielded results that depended heavily on the starting guess for the function solver, so we realized this was an indication of many local minima in the function, seeing that the function never optimized to the same final value twice.

A Nelder-Mead method [7] was attempted in the optimization of this objective function. The `fminsearch` algorithm which is part of the basic MATLAB optimization toolbox was used. It ran very quickly, but had issues with apparently getting stuck in local minima, as evidenced by attempting different starting points and the optimizer finding different optimum values for each starting point.

Due to the shortcomings of the gradient-based constrained optimization and the Nelder-Mead algorithm, a genetic algorithm was the next optimizer implemented in the minimization of our function. The default `ga` optimizer in MATLAB's global optimization package was used, and worked extremely well. Repeatedly, the genetic optimizer converged on the same minimized value, no matter which inputs or parameters were fed into the function. This was extremely gratifying to see, but it has the drawback of taking a long time to properly

converge on a solution. With the intent of using the optimizer in real time while delivering power to the rover’s wheels, an optimization taking longer than a couple of seconds to run isn’t feasible.

Given these limitations, building a surrogate-based optimizer was attempted. This decision was reached late in the process of developing this project, and unfortunately never reached completion. A linear, a quadric, cubic, and quartic surrogate, were all attempted to minimize the target function but none of the surrogates converged on the same value multiple times. The next steps to develop a functional surrogate-based optimizer would be to test further surrogate functions. Exponential, logarithmic, and sinusoidal functions could all be potential successful surrogates. The difficulty in finding a functional surrogate, again, comes from the impossibility of knowing the shape of the six-dimensional function in question. Unfortunately, this piece of the project remains incomplete, but a surrogate optimizer, if functional, would have several advantages over the genetic algorithm currently in use. The principal advantage is speed. A surrogate-based optimizer would run much more quickly than the existing genetic algorithm, with much less computation cost. It remains to be seen if a surrogate-based optimizer could run quickly enough to use for real-time power distribution optimization.

B. Kinematic Arm Calibration

1) *Model*: The kinematic calibration of the BYU Mars Rover manipulator has been performed in simulation, with the expectation that future work will calibrate the physical arm. For this optimization, the objective is to minimize the error between the homogeneous transformation representing the pose of the gripper in the base frame as given by the known motor positions (using forward kinematics) and the homogeneous transformation given by a stereo camera. It was assumed that the transformation from the base of the arm to a stereo camera is known based on the approach in [6] and that the registration of the camera is accurate.

The forward kinematics were calculated from the joint angles using the MATLAB Robotics Toolbox [8]. This Toolbox allows for a robot structure to be defined with a function that has link lengths as inputs, and a single function call returns a 4x4 homogeneous transformation that defines the pose of the end effector with respect to the base given a set of joint angles \hat{q} .

For the purposes of simulation, the “true” geometric parameters of the arm are known, and they were used to calculate the true forward kinematics in the same manner described in the preceding paragraph. These forward kinematics simulate information from a stereo camera that measures the position and orientation of the gripper with respect to the base of the arm. The true value of the link lengths was set to the following. All units are meters.

$$\hat{a} = [0.4816, 0.4127, 0.0980, 0.1595, 0.1967] \quad (3)$$

which was slightly different than the designed geometric parameters \hat{a}^* .

$$\hat{a}^* = [0.5, 0.4, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2] \quad (4)$$

With the forward kinematics calculated from the motor joint angles and the forward kinematics calculated from a camera, we can calculate an error:

$$\hat{e} = {}^bH_{e,measured} - {}^bH_e^* \quad (5)$$

Where ${}^bH_{e,measured}$ is the transformation from the base of the arm to the end effector as measured by the motor encoders, and ${}^bH_e^*$ is the true transformation from the base to the end effector as given by the stereo camera. In order to minimize a scalar value, the 4x4 matrix e was made positive redefined as its own maximum value.

$$e = \max(abs(\hat{e})) \quad (6)$$

Each element in ${}^bH_{e,measured}$ is a function of both the vector of joint angles \hat{q} and the vector of link lengths \hat{a} . To avoid a solution that favors a single joint configuration, a Latin-Hypercube sample of 20 joint configurations was used, and the error was redefined again as the 95th percentile of the 20 errors as calculated by Equation 6.

An optimization is then performed to minimize the maximum element in the 4x4 matrix representing the error between the measured and true homogeneous transformations by varying the link lengths. Upper and lower bounds are added because it is unlikely that the true values for link lengths be different from the designed values by more than 10 cm and it is infeasible for the lengths to be less than zero.

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \text{prctile}(e, 95) \\ \text{w.r.t. } \quad & x \\ \text{s.t. } \quad & x < x_{ub} \\ & x > x_{lb} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where

$$x_{ub} = [0.6, 0.5, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3]' \quad (8)$$

and

$$x_{lb} = [0.4, 0.3, 0, 0, 0.1]' \quad (9)$$

2) *Optimization Procedure*: With the optimization problem set up, we implemented three different algorithms available in MATLAB: `fmincon`, a constrained gradient-based optimizer, `fminsearch`, an application of the gradient-free Nelder-Mead Simplex method [7], and `ga`, a genetic algorithm optimizer. The `fmincon` analysis was performed using the `sqp` algorithm and a step tolerance of $1e - 16$, with 10,000 being the maximum number of function evaluations and other options set to default. The `fminsearch` algorithm was run with a function tolerance and step tolerance of $1e - 12$, with other settings being default. The `ga` algorithm was run with default options. The `fmincon` and `fminsearch` functions require a starting point, and the designed geometry parameters \hat{a}^* was used in these cases.

IV. RESULTS

A. Wheel Control

First, examining the `fmincon` optimizer, it is clear from the three plots shown 3, 4, and 5, each with a different stopping point, that the optimizer regularly optimizes to the same final value, but the minimum value found of around 7 is not acceptable, when it is known that the actual function minimum approaches zero. This means there should be no difference between desired rotation rates and the actual rotation rates at the true optimum of the objective function.

Fig. 3. Minimum function value of wheel control problem vs. Iteration for `fmincon` start: 8V

Fig. 4. Minimum function value of wheel control problem vs. Iteration for `fmincon` start: 25V

Similarly, the following plots, 6, 7, and 8, show the performance of the Nelder-Mead optimization method, which again varies widely depending on the starting point. Notably, this method runs fairly quickly, but it still does not consistently optimize to the same minimum, nor is the function value close enough to the known possible minimum of zero. Instead, the minimum function values found range between 0.4 and 3, depending on the starting point and how many iterations are allowed by the options set. As seen in the plots, this

Fig. 5. Minimum function value of wheel control problem vs. Iteration for `fmincon` start: 30V

Fig. 6. Minimum function value of wheel control problem vs. Iteration for `fminsearch` start: 8V

method was also not acceptable for finding the minimum of the objective function

Finally, the genetic algorithm returns an excellent optimum, as shown in 9. The only drawback, as discussed in the methods section, is the speed at which the algorithm runs, which is too slow to run in real time to optimize power distribution to the wheels.

B. Arm Calibration

The arm calibration optimization was performed using three different optimizers available in MATLAB: `fmincon`, `fminsearch`, and `ga`. All three optimizers converged to essentially the same solution, but there were marked differences in efficiency, as shown in Table I.

Table I shows that the `fmincon` function was by far the most efficient. It converged to a minimum error four orders of magnitude smaller than the gradient-free optimizers, and it did so in one third the number of function calls required by `fminsearch` and one twentieth the number of function calls used by the genetic algorithm. Convergence plots are shown in Figures 10, 11, and 12.

Fig. 7. Minimum function value of wheel control problem vs. Iteration for *fminsearch* start: 25V

Fig. 9. Fitness value of wheel control problem vs. Generation for *ga* optimization algorithm

Fig. 8. Minimum function value of wheel control problem vs. Iteration for *fminsearch* start: 30V

Fig. 10. Function value as a function of iterations to solve the arm calibration using the constrained gradient-based optimizer.

Despite the differences in efficiency, all three optimizers were able to converge to essentially the same solution. This was due to the Latin-Hypercube sampling of joint angles and the averaging of error in the objective function. When this sampling method was not used, the three optimizers found different solutions. The solutions are outlined in Table II.

The absolute error with the known true link geometries are outlined in Table III. As it can be seen, *fmincon* is accurate to at least 0.05 mm, while the gradient-based optimizers are slightly less accurate.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF CONVERGENCE OF THREE DIFFERENT OPTIMIZERS FOR THE ARM CALIBRATION PROBLEM.

Function	Objective Value	Function Calls
<i>fmincon</i>	1.669e-8	518
<i>fminsearch</i>	2.6723e-4	~1500
<i>ga</i>	1.0908e-4	10700

V. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

In this paper, two different optimizations have been presented that, when implemented together on the BYU Mars Rover, will improve the vehicle’s ability to succeed in the Extreme Retrieval Mission of the University Rover Challenge, which is held annually at the Mars Desert Research Station

TABLE II
SOLUTIONS TO THE ARM CALIBRATION PROBLEM

Algorithm	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5
<i>fmincon</i>	0.4816	0.4127	0.0980	0.1595	0.1967
<i>fminsearch</i>	0.4816	0.4127	0.0985	0.1598	0.1973
<i>ga</i>	0.4814	0.4133	0.0978	0.1595	0.1969

TABLE III
ABSOLUTE ERROR BETWEEN THE KNOWN SOLUTION AND THE OPTIMIZER CALIBRATION.

Algorithm	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5
<i>fmincon</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>fminsearch</i>	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.0006
<i>ga</i>	-0.0002	0.0006	-0.0002	0	0.0002

Fig. 11. Function value as a function of iterations to solve the arm calibration using the Nelder-Mead gradient-free optimizer.

Fig. 12. Function value as a function of iterations to solve the arm calibration using the genetic algorithm function.

in Hanksville, Utah, USA. A method of determining optimal command velocities to the rover's six wheels has been presented that allows the rover to maintain a constant speed and heading over uneven and unknown terrain. Additionally, a calibration procedure for the manipulator has been presented that will allow the operator to more effectively manipulate objects remotely, and can also allow for automatic visual servoing. Optimization techniques have been used to accomplish both of these objectives. All work has been done in simulation.

The wheel control optimization problem proved much more difficult than originally anticipated. The dynamic nature of the objective function meant that intuiting a function shape was impossible. We discovered that gradient-based optimizations do not work, and it seems like the objective function has many local minima. This means that using optimization methods without multiple starting points caused our optimization to get stuck in the local minima rather than seeking out the global minimum. This was solved by applying a genetic algorithm, and we predict that implementing a surrogate method would also yield favorable results.

A. Future Work

1) *Wheel Control*: The most important next step for this project is finishing a surrogate-based optimizer that will allow for real-time or near real-time power distribution during rover

operation. Future work for wheel control will also include combining power distribution optimization with vehicle kinematics. By doing so, it will be possible to predict moving direction of the vehicle and allow the rover to compensate for error in pilot input. An interesting next step would be to optimize power distribution and heading based on wheel-slip, within pre-set bounds according to the driver input.

2) *Arm Calibration*: Future work for the Arm calibration sub-project will include implementing the calibration in hardware to calibrate the physical arm. This will involve accurate camera registration to obtain the "true" transformation to the gripper. Additionally, an optimization under uncertainty could be performed that accounts for uncertainty in motor encoders as well as the uncertainty stemming from the stereo camera. This paper only explored a calibration of the link lengths of the manipulator. However, further expansion of the problem to include angular offsets at each joint would probably lead to significant improvements in performance.

APPENDIX SOURCE CODE

The source code used for this paper can be found at https://github.com/dsquez/byu_me575

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Iida and R. Tedrake, "Motor control optimization of compliant one-legged locomotion in rough terrain," in *2007 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. IEEE, 2007, pp. 2230–2235.
- [2] C. Lin and X. Cheng, "A traction control strategy with an efficiency model in a distributed driving electric vehicle," *The Scientific World Journal*, vol. 2014, 2014.
- [3] G. Taylor, L. Kleeman *et al.*, "Flexible self-calibrated visual servoing for a humanoid robot," in *Australian conference on robotics and automation (ACRA2001)*. Citeseer, 2001, pp. 79–84.
- [4] J.-M. Renders, E. Rossignol, M. Becquet, R. Hanus *et al.*, "Kinematic calibration and geometrical parameter identification for robots," *IEEE Transactions on robotics and automation*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 721–732, 1991.
- [5] B. Du, J. Zhao, and C. Song, "Optimal base placement and motion planning for mobile manipulators," in *ASME 2012 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference*. American Society of Mechanical Engineers Digital Collection, 2012, pp. 1227–1234.
- [6] N. Dantam, H. B. Amor, H. Christensen, and M. Stilman, "Online camera registration for robot manipulation," in *Experimental Robotics*. Springer, 2016, pp. 179–194.
- [7] J. A. Nelder and R. Mead, "A simplex method for function minimization," *The computer journal*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 308–313, 1965.
- [8] P. I. Corke, *Robotics, Vision & Control: Fundamental Algorithms in MATLAB*. Springer, 2011, ISBN 978-3-642-20143-1.

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